

THE TREMENDOUS CONTRIBUTION OF STEPHANIE MEYER TO THE GENRE OF SCIENCE FICTION. THE USAGE OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY AND THEIR SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF THE NOVEL “THE HOST”

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ABSTRACT

American literature has always attracted the attention of readers with its various kinds of famous works, the sharp pen and breath of writers. Stephanie Meyer, one of the creators who was able to describe the events of her time both artistically and scientifically, is also one of the most influential writers in American literature. This article analyzes Stephanie Meyer's contribution to science fiction in American literature through her work “The Host”.

Keywords: modernism, postmodernism, science fiction, parasitic alien race, medical terminology, synonyms.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Американская литература всегда привлекала внимание читателей своими разного рода известными произведениями, острым пером и дыханием писателей. Стефани Майер, одна из творцов, сумевших описать события своего времени как в художественном, так и в научном плане, также является одним из самых влиятельных писателей в американской литературе. В этой статье анализируется вклад Стефани Майер в научную фантастику в американской литературе через ее произведение «Гостья».

Ключевые слова: модернизм, постмодернизм, научная фантастика, паразитическая инопланетная раса, медицинская терминология, синонимы.

INTRODUCTION

Modern American literature includes twentieth and twenty-first century fiction, poetry, and drama. The period is marked by two significant aesthetic movements:

modernism and **postmodernism**. Modernism describes the avant-garde styles of the early twentieth century, while postmodernism describes the period of art that evolved after World War II.

American literature comprises all the written works produced in the United States and its preceding colonies. “American literature is very important for the education of people as it reveals the culture and history of the United States¹³”.

One of the most outstanding American representatives, Stephanie Meyer, was a writer who wrote many popular plays in the direction of vampire romance, young adult fiction, science fiction. S. Meyer is an American novelist and film producer. She is best known for writing the vampire romance series *Twilight*, which has sold over 100 million copies, with translations into 37 different languages. Meyer was the bestselling author of 2008 and 2009 in the U.S., having sold over 29 million books in 2008, and 26.5 million in 2009.

Furthermore, if we write about her contribution to the genre of science fiction, without any hesitation, we should emphasize her novel “*The Host*”. It is Stephanie Meyer’s first work of science fiction. It tells the story of a parasitic form of alien that has invaded earth determined to put an end to the violence inherent in the human species, and the humans determined to resist occupation. The book is about Earth, in a post-apocalyptic time, being invaded by a parasitic alien race known as Souls, and follows one Soul’s predicament when the consciousness of her human host refuses to give up her body. The book is inspired by the 1963 Italian film *Omicron*.

Meyer has said that she is working on additional books in “*The Host*” series and that she intends to write a trilogy. She said in an interview that, if published, the first sequel would be entitled “*The Seeker*” and the second “*The Soul*”. In November 2009, she said, “*I’d like to eventually have The Host be part of a trilogy*.” In February 2011, Meyer stated that she had outlines for the sequels and had done some writing on them.

“*The Host*” was released on May 6, 2008, with an initial print run of 750,000 copies. An international version of the novel was released on April 2, 2009, in the United Kingdom, Ireland, Indonesia, the Philippines, Australia and Hong Kong by the UK publishing division. It was translated into many languages.

METHODS

Writer Stephanie Meyer has been able to show unique examples of creativity with different approaches in each of his works. Turning to her now-analyzed work, “*The Host*”, this work is a shining example of science fiction.

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Now, we tend to analyze several scientific terms used in the novel applying semantic method of classification so as to indicate which sphere of terminology they belong to.

Table 1. The usage of medical terminology and their semantic analysis in the novel “The Host”.

№	The scientific (medical) terms applied in the novel	The definition of scientific terms
1.	Grimace (v)	To make an ugly expression with your face to show pain
2.	Billow (v)	To fill with air and smell out
3.	Cryotank (n)	In science fiction, cryogenic tanks are used to freeze people. A cryotank or cryogenic tank is a tank that is used to store material at very low temperatures
4.	Sedate (v)	To give someone drugs in order to make calm or to make them sleep
5.	Dial (n)	A similar control on a machine that shows measurement of time, temperature, speed
6.	Agony (n)	Extremephysical or mental pain
7.	Gleam (n)	An expression of particular feeling or emotion that shows in somebody’s eyes
8.	Anatomy (n)	A scientific study of the structure of human or animal bodies
9.	Vein (n)	Any of the tubes that carry blood from all parts of the body towards the heart
10.	Airway (n)	The passage from the nose and throat to the lungs through which you breathe
11.	Flail (v)	To move your arms and legs around without control
12.	Trauma (n)	A mental condition caused by severe shock, especially when the harmful effects last for a long time
13.	Euphoria (n)	An extremely strong feeling of happiness and excitement that usually lasts only a short time

14.	Sulphur (n)	A pale yellow substance that produces a strong unpleasant smell when it burns and is used in medicine and industry
15.	Hibernation (n)	A state like deep sleep

The table below provides information about the synonyms applied in the work.

No	Synonyms which are used in the novel "The Host"	The meaning of the synonyms
1.	Gawk – glare – stare – look at	To look at smb or something
2.	Murmur - mutter - whisper	To say something in a soft quiet voice
3.	Glisten - shine - brighten	To produce or reflect light
4.	Unfathomable - strange - odd	Unusual in a way that is difficult to understand
5.	Host - denizen – inhabitant	A person, an animal or plant that lives in a particular place
6.	Vigilant - watchful - alert	Very careful to notice any signs of danger
7.	Scared - terrified - feared	Frightened of something
8.	Reverberate - echo	To be repeated several times as it is reflected off different surfaces
9.	Sterile - odorless	Completely clean and free from bacteria
10.	Confuse - distract	To make something or someone change direction

DISCUSSION

It would be expedient to use excerpts from the works to better interpret and understand these terms. For instance,

1. *"Like a living ribbon, she twisted and rippled, stretching, happy to be free of **the cryotank**".* (the term which is used in medicine to freeze people)¹⁴.

2. *"The blackness swallowed up **the agony**, and I was seak with gratitude that memory had come to this most final of conclusions¹⁵".* (Extremephysical or mental pain).

¹⁴ Meyer Stephanie, "The Host", 237 Park Avenue, New York, NY 10017, May 2008. P. -13

¹⁵ Meyer Stephanie, "The Host", 237 Park Avenue, New York, NY 10017, May 2008. P. -18

3. “A strange feeling tickled through **my veins** at the sound. (Any of the tubes that carry blood from all parts of the body towards the heart)¹⁶”.

4. “She is very strong. Others have had much more **trauma**, with much less cause”. (A mental condition caused by severe shock, especially when the harmful effects last for a long time)¹⁷.

5. “Suddenly he gasps, and wonders if any of **my flailing** limbs have made contact¹⁸”. (To move your arms and legs around without control)

Through these examples, we can see that a writer can convey scientific terms accurately and precisely, as well as artistically, in writing a work. This shows that she also has a lot of knowledge in the field of science.

Let’s analyze the results of **second table** with examples taken from the novel. For example,

1. “Maybe, he says, and continues to **stare** at Uncle Jeb’s squiggles. – His eyes swept around the cave, where a few people lingered by the exits, **gawking** at us.

2. “She is going to be even more **scared** when she sees all of you. Not like the beginning, when I **feared** her and wished for her eradication from my mind.

3. “Jared watched me go with an **unfathomable** expression. Again, the **strange** conviction that she would live long after I was gone swept through me”.

So, the frequent use of synonyms in the play means that Stephanie Meyer has a lot of vocabulary, a wide range of artistic worldview. At the same time, it is an art for the writer to use these synonyms wisely, that is, to use them correctly in their positive and negative places.

CONCLUSION

Thus, Stephanie Meyer is an author and film producer who is the most famous for writing the different novels in different genres. All her novels, have taken readers around the world into a journey of fantasy and everlasting love and have driven millions of its fans. Due to the success her books, Stephanie Meyer has gained numerous awards and recognitions that have established her as one the most successful writers of modernism period. Her novels have all been adapted into big screen. Her books have greatly impacted society, setting trends and social standards.

Stephanie Meyer, who is able to show that she is so talented, as well as in science, has a deep knowledge, will remain forever in the hearts of readers, I think.

¹⁶ Meyer Stephanie, “The Host”, 237 Park Avenue, New York, NY 10017, May 2008. P. -677

¹⁷ As above. P. -20

¹⁸ As above. P. -42

REFERENCES

1. Yugay , E. 2021. Цифровая культура и общество: проблемы их взаимоотношений в условиях глобализации. Общество и инновации. 2, 7/S (авг. 2021), 58–67. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss7/S-pp58-67>.
2. Meyer Stephanie, “The Host”, 237 Park Avenue, New York, NY 10017, May 2008.
3. Diane Roback. Children’s bestsellers 2009: The reign continues. Weekly, 2010.
4. Keith Brooke, “The Host” by Stephanie Meyer, The Guardian, August 1, 2009.
5. Luciano, Le Aura. 5 Things you should know about “The Host”. Latina. March 28, 2013
6. Meyer Stephanie, “The Host”, 237 Park Avenue, New York, NY 10017, May 2008.